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assumed to be negligible. The solutions employed were so dilute that the formation of any polynuclear species could be ignored.

The $\log K_1$ values were calculated by using expression $\log \frac{\bar{n}}{1-\bar{n}} = \log K_1 - pL$ and plotting a graph for \bar{n} values between 0.2 to 0.8. The $\log K_1$ values obtained are presented in Table 1.

In the systems studied only 1 : 1 complexes were formed. The possibility of 1 : 2 complexes cannot be considered since \bar{n} values higher than 1 were erratic and fell near the pH of hydrolysis.

*log K = a.pK + b relation*⁵: In the rare earth chelates of substituted methoxy benzoic acids the plots of $\log K$ vs pK gave straight line relationship in every case. The slopes lie between 0.85 and 0.95. The almost identical magnitude of the slopes for the various lanthanide chelates of methoxy substituted benzoic acids, indicates similar nature of the chelates and the mode of dissociation of different ligands.⁶⁻⁸

Jones *et al*⁹ have suggested on the basis of purely electrostatic model that the slope value will increase with increasing cationic charge and decreasing distance of separation (equal to the radius of cation plus a constant). The slope values for Cx^{2+} methoxy benzoic acid complexes by present authors was 0.45¹⁰. The higher charge on rare earth cations is expected to give a higher value of slope. Hence the slope values for rare earth cations are higher than that of the Cu^{2+} .

As is often the case a break in regular change of properties of rare earth occurs at gadolinium. It has been observed that the Gd^{3+} chelates of all the ligands have lower $\log K$ values as compared to those of Sm^{3+} and Dy^{3+} . Linear discontinuity is found in a plot of $\log K$ vs e^2/r .

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Synthesis of Cyclohepta [b] Thiophen Derivatives

P. K. SEN* and BANDANA KUNDU
Department of Chemistry, Presidency College, Calcutta-700 073
and
TAPAN K. DAS
Department of Chemistry, Calcutta National Medical College,
Calcutta-700 014

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IN connection with our investigation in the fields of dehydrogenation¹ and desulphurization reactions, several cyclohepta [b] thiophen derivatives were needed. Here we report the synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-6,6-spirocyclopentane-4H-cyclohepta [b] thiophen-4-one (7), 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-6.6-spirocyclopentane-4H-cyclohepta[b] thiophen (10) and their alkyl derivatives by an adaptation of the method developed earlier¹ in this laboratory, for the synthesis of benzene analogue of the above compounds. Recently synthesis and photochemical behaviour of cyclohepta [b] thiophen-4-ones were reported by Jones and co-worker².

To synthesise the keto acid (1) we have studied the Friedel-Craft condensation of cyclopentane-1,1-diacetic anhydride with thiophen under different experimental conditions (vide Table 1). Aluminium chloride and stannic chloride catalysed reactions gave some unidentified polymeric material containing sulphur. When BF_3 -etherate was used as a catalyst, no condensation product was isolated. The keto acid (1) was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure to the pentanoic acid (4). The acid chloride of the reduced acid was cyclised using stannic chloride to give the cyclic ketone (7). Preparation of the acid chloride by oxalyl chloride method had improved the yield and quality of the cyclic product [vide experimental, compounds (10) and (11)]. The cyclic ketone was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure to the spiran (10).

- (1) R = H
(2) R = Me
(3) R = Et

- (4) R = H
(5) R = Me
(6) R = Et

- (7) R = H
(8) R = Me
(9) R = Et

- (10) R = H
(11) R = Me
(12) R = Et

In a similar manner, 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-methyl-6,6-spirocyclopentane-4H-cyclohepta [b] thiophen(11) and 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-ethyl 6,6-spirocyclopentane-4H-cyclohepta [b] thiophen (12) were synthesised starting from appropriate alkylthiophen and cyclopentane-1,1-diacetic anhydride. The structures of the keto acids (1-3) and cyclohepta [b] thiophen-4-ones (7-9) were confirmed by UV, IR and NMR spectra.

Experimental

Alkyl thiophenes⁵ and ester acid chloride of cyclopentane-1,1-diacetic acid⁶ were prepared by the methods indicated. Light petroleum refers to the fraction, b.p. 60-80°. Ethereal extracts were dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Analytical data of the compounds (1-12) were all within experimental error.

3, 3-Cyclopentane-5-(2-thienyl)-5-oxopentanoic acid (1): To a vigorously stirred solution of thiophen (7.9g, 0.09 m) and cyclopentane-1, 1-diacetic anhydride (13 g, 0.08 m) in nitrobenzene (85 ml) at 0° was added aluminium chloride (24.8 g, 0.19 m) slowly in parts. The mixture was stirred further for one hour, hydrolysed with ice-hydrochloric acid, and steam distilled to remove the solvent. The crude product after filtration was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution and filtered, charcoalised and finally acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The solid product was obtained by filtration and on recrystallisation from light petroleum gave the keto acid (1). m.p. 82° (14 g., 72%)

λ_{\max} 262 m μ (log ϵ . 3.8); ν_{\max} (Nuzol) 1640 and 1680 cm⁻¹; δ 1.65 (8H, s, ring cyclopentane), 2.7 (2H, s, CH₂, COOH), 3.18 (2H, s, COCH₂), 7.2 (1H, m, Arproton), 7.7 (2H, m, Ar-proton) and 11.2 ppm (1H, s, COOH).

Methyl ester of (1) was prepared by diazomethane, b.p. 158°/1 mm. (CCl₄) 3.5 ppm (3H, s, -COOCH₃).

3, 3-Cyclopentane-5-(2-thienyl) pentanoic acid (4): A mixture of diethylene glycol (55 ml) and potassium hydroxide (9.1 g) was heated carefully until the potassium hydroxide began to melt and went into solution. The solution was then cooled to 80-100° and to it were added the keto acid (1) (12 g, 0.05 m) and 100% hydrazine hydrate (9.9 ml) and the mixture was heated under reflux for one hour. Then the mixture was distilled sufficiently slowly till the liquid temperature had reached 205-210° and the mixture was then heated under reflux for 3 hours. The liquid temperature during refluxing was maintained in the range 190-205°. The cooled mixture was poured into water and washed with ether; the aqueous layer was acidified and the product was extracted with ether. The dried ether extract on distillation gave the pentanoic acid (4) which slowly solidified, b.p. 151°/0.4 mm.; m.p. 52° (10.4 g, 92%)

5, 6, 7, 8-Tetrahydro-6, 6-spirocyclopentane-4H-cyclohepta [b] thiophen-4-one(7): To a solution of the above pentanoic acid (4) (10.2 g, 0.043 m) in ether (35 ml), purified thionyl chloride (6.8 ml) and pyridine (several drops) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hours after which solvent and the excess thionyl chloride were removed in vacuo. The crude acid chloride was dissolved in dry carbon disulphide (200 ml) and cooled to 0°. Stannic chloride (9.4 ml) was added dropwise with vigorous stirring, and then allowed the mixture to come to room temperature and stirred for another 2½ hours. Ice and hydrochloric acid were added and the organic layer was separated, washed with dil. hydrochloric acid, water, sodium bicarbonate solution, then with water and finally dried and distilled to give the cycloheptathiophenone (7), which slowly solidified, b.p. 126°/0.3 mm., m.p. 50° (5.2 g, 55%).

λ_{\max} 255 m μ (log ϵ , 3.9); ν_{\max} 1670 cm⁻¹; δ 1.65 (8H, s, cyclopentane, ring), 1.8 (2H, t, C₇ methylene), 2.6 (2H, s, COCH₂), 2.9 (2H, t, ArCH₂), 7.0 (1H, d, Ar-proton) and 7.3 ppm (1H, d, Ar-proton) 2,4-D,N.P. derivative of the ketone (7) was crystallised from ethylacetate-alcohol mixture, m.p. 162°.

5, 6, 7, 8-Tetrahydro-6, 6-spirocyclopentane-4H-cyclohepta[b] thiophen (10): The ketone (7) (5 g; 0.024 m) was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure as described in the reduction of the keto acid (1) using diethylene glycol (28 ml) potassium hydroxide (4.8 g) and 100% hydrazine hydrate (5.5 ml). After reaction, the cold mixture was poured into water and extracted with ether. The dried ether extract on distillation gave the compound (10), b.p. 104°/0.4 mm. (4.5 g, 96%).

3,3-Cyclopentane-5-(5-methyl-2-thienyl)-5-oxopentanoic acid (2): Prepared as described for the keto acid (1) from 2-methylthiophen and cyclopentane (1,1-diacetic anhydride in 63% yield. The keto acid (2) had m.p. 78° (from benzene-light petroleum). ν_{\max} 1640 and 1700 cm⁻¹; δ 1.65 (8H, s, cyclopentane ring) 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃) 2.58 (2H, s, CH₂

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TABLE—1 FRIEDEL-CRAFT CONDENSATION OF ANHYDRIDE AND ESTER-ACID CHLORIDE DERIVATIVE OF CYCLOPENTANE-1, 1-DIACETIC ACID WITH THIOPHEN UNDER DIFFERENT EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

Acylating agent	Catalyst	Solvent	Temp. °C	% yield of (1)	% of the unreacted acylating agent	% of the acylating agent lost due to polymer formation
Anhydride	AlCl ₃	Nitrobenzene	0°	72	-	28
"	SnCl ₄	S-Tetrachloro ethane	0°	13.3	54.7 ^a	32
"	"	Benzene	5-10°	15.4	60 ^a	24.6
Ester-acid chloride	"	"	0-5°	75.7 ^b	-	24.3
Anhydride	BF ₃ .etherate	Toluene	0°C		99.5 ^d	

Isolated in the form of acid, ^b Product isolated as keto ester, ^c Following the method of Heid and Levine^{3,4},
^d Isolated as the anhydride.

COOH) 3.05 (2H, s, COCH₃) 6.75 (1H, d, Ar-proton) 7.55 (1H, d, Ar-proton) and 11.0 ppm. (1H, s, COOH).

3, 3-Cyclopentane-5-(5-methyl-2-thienyl) pentanoic acid (5): Prepared by Huang-Minlon reduction of the keto acid (2) by the method described earlier in 80% yield. The acid (5) had b.p. 187°/1.2 mm.

5, 6, 7, 8-Tetrahydro-2-methyl-6, 6-spirocyclopentane-4H-cyclohepta [b] thiophen-4-one (8): A solution of the pentanoic acid (5) (13.9 g, 0.055 m) in dry benzene (75 ml), and pyridine (4.35 g; 0.055m) was added dropwise to a well stirred solution of oxalyl chloride (11.7 g, 0.092 m) in dry benzene (60 ml) at room-temperature. The mixture was stirred for further one hour, filtered to remove pyridine hydrochloride. The solvent and excess oxalyl chloride were removed in vacuum. The crude acid chloride was cyclised to the ketone (8) in 80% yield by the stannic chloride method described earlier. The ketone (8) had b.p. 158°/1.2 mm. (10.3 g, 80%) which slowly solidified, m.p. 52°. 2,4-DNP derivative of (8) had m.p. 210° (cryst. from ethylacetate)

λ_{\max} 257 m μ (log ϵ , 4.1); ν_{\max} 1670 cm⁻¹; δ 1.6 (8H, s, cyclopentane ring) 1.8 (2H, t, C₇ methylene) 2.4 (3H, s, Ar.CH₃) 2.6 (2H, s, COCH₃) 2.9 (2H, t, Ar.CH₂) and 7.0 ppm. (1H, s, Ar-proton).

5, 6, 7, 8-Tetrahydro-2-methyl-6,6-spirocyclopentane-4H-cyclohepta [b] thiophen (11): The cyclic ketone (8) was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure to give the spiran (11) in 93% yield. It had b.p. 140°/1.3 mm.

3, 3-Cyclopentane-5(5-ethyl-2-thienyl)-5-oxopentanoic acid (3): Prepared from 2-ethylthiophen and cyclopentane-1, 1-diacetic anhydride in 74% yield. The keto acid (3) had m.p. 90° (from benzene-light petroleum) ν_{\max} 1630 and 1700 cm⁻¹; δ 1.4 (3H, t, CH₃ of ethyl) 1.65 (8H, s, cyclopentane ring) 2.18 (2H, s, CH₂COOH) 2.85 (2H, m, -CH₂ of ethyl) 3.05 (2H, s, COCH₃) 6.8 (1H, d, Ar-proton) 7.55

(1H, d, Ar-proton) and 11.0 ppm. (1H, s, -COOH). The keto acid (3) gave methyl ester b.p. 180°/1 mm.

3, 3-Cyclopentane-5-(5-ethyl-2-thienyl) pentanoic acid (6): Reduction of the keto acid (3) by Huang-Minlon procedure gave the reduced acid (6) in 94% yield. b.p. 173°/1 mm.

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-ethyl-6, 6-spirocyclopentane-4H-cyclohepta [b] thiophen-4-one (9): The reduced acid (6) was converted to the acid chloride by oxalyl chloride method and finally cyclised to the cyclic ketone (9) by stannic chloride in 84% yield. It had b.p. 165°/1.2 mm. λ_{\max} 258 m μ (log ϵ , 3.98); ν_{\max} 1675 cm⁻¹; δ 1.2 (3H, t, CH₃ of ethyl) 1.65 (8H, s, cyclopentane ring) 1.8 (2H, t, C₇ methylene) 2.65 (2H, s, COCH₃) 2.55-2.8 (2H, m, Ar.CH₂) 2.9 (2H, t, Ar.CH₂) and 7.0 ppm. (1 H, s, Arproton).

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-ethyl-6, 6-spirocyclopentane-4H-cyclohepta [b] thiophen (12): Huang-Minlon reduction of the cyclic ketone (9) gave the spiran (12) in 86% yield. It had b.p. 141°/1 mm.

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